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Knowledge Broker

MINIMUM VIABLE SKILLS PROFILE

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This booklet is part of the **Skills4EOSC collection of Minimum Viable Skills Profiles (MVS)**, which outline key Open Science competencies for different professional roles. It presents a focused extract from the **Annex to Deliverable D2.6**, designed to support usability and communication. To explore the full list of profiles, visit the Skills4EOSC website (<https://www.skills4eosC.eu/resources/publications/mvs>) or consult the full Annex (<https://zenodo.org/records/15761916>).

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LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

CARE	Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, and Ethics	MVS	Minimum Viable Skillset
CSCCE	Centre for Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement	ORCC	Open Research Competencies Coalition
DMP	Data Management Plan	OS	Open Science
ELSI	Ethical, Legal and Social Issues	R&I	Research and Innovation
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud	RDA	Research Data Alliance
ETHRD IG	Education and Training on Handling of Research Data Interest Group (RDA)	RDM	Research Data Management
ICT	Information and Communication Technology	RI	Research Infrastructure
IT	Information Technology	RPO	Research Performing Organisation
JRC	Joint Research Centre	RSE	Research Software Engineer
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable	T4fs	Terms for FAIR skills

1. Introduction

| Open Science mission for this role

Knowledge Brokers serve as vital intermediaries in the transfer of knowledge between experts and stakeholders. They are responsible for facilitating the dissemination of scientific information, ensuring that research findings are accessible and actionable for various audiences. **Knowledge Brokers promote transparency and collaboration**, particularly in the context of Open Science, by bridging the gap between research and practice, enabling informed decision-making. They strive to provide unbiased and reliable information, fostering trust among stakeholders while adhering to ethical standards in knowledge sharing.

The Minimum Viable Skillset (MVS) recognises the competencies essential for individuals or teams acting as intermediaries in the knowledge transfer process. The term “knowledge broker” refers to individuals or teams who, in a variety of contexts, facilitate the transfer of knowledge from experts to a wider audience. This practice encompasses diverse use cases with the common objective of disseminating scientific information and facilitating its use in society. Typical scenarios include appointed individual experts or expert groups informing public authorities or agencies about scientific findings, as well as aggregating research data to provide an overview of specific phenomena or fields. Such efforts support evidence-based decision-making and provide trustworthy and understandable information to laypeople.

Knowledge Brokers typically use their expertise to connect stakeholders with the information and resources they need to make informed decisions. They fill the gaps between science and various stakeholders, including policymakers, practitioners, and the public. Sometimes, groups, such as committees or learned societies, undertake this role.

A notable subtype within this field is the “Honest Broker.” **An Honest Broker serves as an impartial mediator, facilitating communication and decision-making among individuals or groups with differing interests or values.** They maintain neutrality and bias-free positions, providing all parties with accurate information to help negotiate and find common ground. This role is especially critical in situations requiring fair and transparent processes, such as conflict resolution or public policy development.

Knowledge Brokers operate within various organizational contexts, including ministries, governmental organizations, research-performing organizations, national agencies, national funding organizations, communication/media agencies, and committees or learned societies.

In relation to Open Science, the Knowledge Broker plays a crucial role in bridging the gap between research and practice by connecting researchers with stakeholders who can benefit from their work. They help create a more open, transparent, and collaborative research environment, leading to more effective and impactful research outcomes. This may involve collaborating closely with researchers to translate findings into actionable recommendations or providing policymakers with access to the latest accessible scientific evidence to inform decision-making. Additionally, knowledge brokers may promote Open Science practices within their organizations or communities, advocating for open access publishing, developing data-sharing policies, and supporting dissemination of research findings to a wider audience.

KNOWLEDGE BROKER

ASSOCIATED FUNCTION TITLES:

Knowledge Broker, Honest Broker, Research Liaison, Information Specialist, Policy Advisor, Evidence Synthesis Expert, Science Communicator, Stakeholder Engagement Coordinator.

ESSENTIAL SKILLS FOR THIS ROLE

- Familiarity with policy making practices and procedures.
- Understanding of open, ethical and responsible research principles.
- Managing considerable amount of information related to OS practices.
- Searching, retrieving, appraising and synthesizing evidence.
- Developing and maintaining network of researchers, policymakers, and other stakeholders to help the promotion and implementation of OS practices and support for co-creation activities.
- Providing training and education to researchers, policymakers, and public citizens about OS practices.
- Evaluating research findings and identifying potential conflicts of interest.
- Tailoring resources to local needs and assessing the implementation context.

SOFT / TRANSVERSAL SKILLS

Considered equally important by Skills4EOSC, these are not specific to the occupation or sector.

- Communication
- Collaboration
- Leadership
- Self-confidence
- Citizens and stakeholders engagement
- Influencing
- Negotiation and diplomacy

- Problem-solving
- Innovative thinking
- Analytical and research skills
- Adaptability to changes
- Stakeholder management and influencing
- Facilitation

BACKGROUND ASSUMPTIONS

MAIN ACTIVITIES

- Bridging the interface between science and policy by ensuring mutual understanding among these parties.
- Aligning the needs of the policy community with the evidence synthesis provided.
- Ensuring that the policy community have a good understanding of the implications of the evidence proffered.
- Ensuring the quality and transparency of evidence synthesis.
- Ensuring the evidence synthesis has appropriate expert inputs.

- Identifying options and providing advice from a scientific viewpoint.
- Identifying constraints, uncertainties and caveats.
- Contextualising the FAIR and OS principles to specific domains.
- Identifying strengths and weaknesses in how OS is applied.
- Identifying needs for change in OS policy or practice in relevant research domains.
- Ensuring all actors are engaged in co-creation actions.

CONTRIBUTES TO WHICH OPEN SCIENCE OUTCOMES?

- Information needs of referenced stakeholders/interlocutors are identified and addressed, by bridging specialised scientific data and information and facilitating the stakeholders' understanding and correct interpretation of this information.
- Concrete policy options are drafted through analysis and evaluation that is based as much as possible on co-creation, continuous knowledge exchange and capacity building.
- Knowledge producers and users are facilitated in an objective and transparent manner, by translating science into accessible and policy-usable knowledge.
- Open Science and FAIR principles are applied in the knowledge production chain to enhance the uptake into public policy of scientifically developed knowledge.
- Policymakers are helped to identify options, and understand the likely impact of choices, by providing advice from a scientific viewpoint.
- Researchers are helped to understand the potential impact on policy makers of their outcomes.
- Through advocacy, FAIR and Open Science principles become related to the organisation's local policies and processes including its research practices and goals.

Further information

OPEN SCIENCE SKILLS TERMS

OS skills terms match the essential skills in this MVS to competence definitions from relevant taxonomies. The selected terms offer further information to help identify the learning objectives for skills development. Sources: European Skills, Competences and Occupations ontology ([ESCO](#)), [ResearchComp](#), [terms4FAIRskills](#), [Center Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement](#).

ESCO Research Skills: [Increase the impact of science on policy and society](#); [Apply research ethics and scientific integrity principles in research activities](#); [Demonstrate disciplinary expertise](#); [Synthesise information](#); [Develop professional network with researchers and scientists](#); [Promote the transfer of knowledge](#); [Promote the participation of citizens in scientific and research activities](#); [Mentor individuals](#); [Teach in academic or vocational contexts](#); [Evaluate research activities](#); [Manage intellectual property rights](#); [Interact professionally in research and professional environments](#).

ESCO Transversal Skills: [Organise information, objects and resources](#); [Demonstrate curiosity](#); [Conduct web searches](#); [Critically evaluate information and its sources](#); [Moderate a discussion](#); [Communicate with a non-scientific audience](#); [Demonstrate intercultural competence](#); [Demonstrate trustworthiness](#); [Make decisions](#); [Motivate others](#); [Show confidence](#); [Plan](#); [Resolve conflicts](#); [Show empathy](#); [Negotiate compromises](#); [Promote ideas, products, services](#); [Respect the diversity of cultural values and norms](#); [Manage time](#).

ResearchComp: [Promote citizen science](#); [Mobilise resources](#).

Terms4FAIRskills: [Data policy](#); [Ethical application of patents, licenses](#); [Information security](#); [Open access publishing](#); [Open peer review](#); [Open innovation](#); [Research integrity, attribution, impact awareness](#); [Research governance](#); [Assessment on FAIR data criteria](#); [Training in open and fair methods](#).

CSCCE: [Consultation and listening](#); [Data analysis](#); [Landscape analysis](#); [Advocacy](#); [Collaboration](#); [Knowledge brokering](#); [Engagement](#); [Moderation, mediation and intervention](#); [Speaking and presenting](#); [Evaluation and assessment](#); [Cultural competence](#); [Meeting facilitation](#); [Record-keeping](#); [Operational planning and implementation](#); [Social media](#); [Content planning](#).

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